

Designing and Controlling an Autonomous Vehicle using Wireless Communication and Motor Encoder Data for Return-to-Home

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Abstract— This research presents the development of a car controlled by human input wirelessly, and later upon request returning back to its starting location autonomously. This return to home functionality aimed to achieve a centimetre level precision with a power efficient and low-cost solution, eliminating the use of a GPS, camera or any other external sensor and relying solely on motor-mounted encoders. An overview of the development procedure for the hardware, software and implementation of the car is presented in this paper.

Keywords—Autonomous; Arduino; ESP32; Microcontroller; Python: Return-to-Home

I. INTRODUCTION

For the last few years, autonomous vehicles have been the subject of interest of many industries and there have been a lot of research and development in this domain. To contribute to these developments, our goal was to design an autonomously operated vehicle that could be used as a testing model and a framework for these new types of vehicles. Our objective was to create a vehicle capable of receiving wireless commands sent manually to move in the environment and return to the original position automatically with a centimeter level precision.

Conventional GPS-based navigation is affected by a range of errors, as illustrated in Fig.1, all of which typically range from 100 to 240 centimeter [9] or more. Additionally, signal delays, cold and hot start waiting times further reduce reliability. Even though RTK (Real-time Kinematic) GPS provides enhanced precision but its cost remains a major limitation.

Another method for navigation uses computer vision which tracks the already placed distinctive markers like visual dots or fiducials which requires significant image processing capability. This approach requires prior environmental preparation, good and stable lighting conditions and clustered environments decreasing accuracy reduces flexibility of this system.

Fig. 1. GPS errors [8]

In some areas infrastructure based localization is used. This requires installing magnetic beacons or towers which the robot uses to determine its location and orientation. Once again, it requires extensive setup and calibration limiting its use in dynamic applications.

Unlike most other similar systems, our design does not utilize expensive and sophisticated GPS, 9-axis gyro-sensors, cameras and other sensors; instead, we used the power efficient and low-cost motor-mounted slit disks and encoders technique to precisely calculate distance and orientation.

Methods	Precision	Cost	Adaptability	Computational Demand
GPS Standard	100–240 cm	Moderate	Limited indoors	Low
RTK GPS	±1–2 cm	High	Limited indoors	Moderate
Vision-Based	±1–10 cm	High	Moderate indoors	High
Magnetic Beacons	±10–20 cm	High	Limited indoors	Moderate
Our Encoder-Based	±2–15 cm	Low	High indoors	Low

Table 1. Comparison of Localization Methods

II. THEORETICAL CONCEPT OF THE VEHICLE MOVEMENT

Our design is a three-wheeled vehicle with two rear tires and a swivel wheel at the front. The vehicle moves by the rotation of the two rear tires controlled by the motors while the front wheel is turned in the direction desired and it just provides support and stability and has no active role in movement. We chose this setup as this enable smooth and flexible movement with just two controlling motors and adjusting their relative speeds.

Command	Left Wheel Direction	Right Wheel Direction
Forward	Forward (+)	Forward (+)
Backward	Backward (-)	Backward (-)
Slight Left	Low-Speed Forward (+)	High-Speed Forward (+)
Slight Right	High-Speed Forward (+)	Low-Speed Forward (+)
Extreme Left	Backward (-)	Forward (+)
Extreme Right	Forward (+)	Backward (-)
Stop	Stop	Stop

Table 2. Wheel Direction Mapping for Motion Commands

This design offers a simple yet very effective system of movement which is especially suited to indoor navigation and small to medium range distances. This design minimizes the need for sophisticated mechanical components while not sacrificing precise mobility. The vehicle can maneuver in tight spaces and return to its original position accurately. Having the driving logic built around just the two rear wheels making the model easier to implement, control and replicate.

Fig 2. Three-wheeled vehicle model in movement. [11]

III. 3D CAD DESIGN OF THE VEHICLE

Individual elements of a vehicle were designed in 3D CAD software. In our case, we used Blender, which is widely used in industry for simulation and presentation purposes. Figure 4 demonstrates the 3D CAD design of the vehicle.

Fig. 3. The basic 3D CAD design of the vehicle

The University of Debrecen, Faculty of Engineering, Air- and Road Vehicles Department [1] 3D printed the parts needed for this research project.

A 4WD (4-wheel drive) robot car chassis kit was used. This chassis design, although made of transparent acrylic, was not only used because of its low cost but also because it has been proven to be efficient and reliable as a part of a large number of coordinated autonomous vehicles, also known as swarm robots [2]. The kit included vertical rotatory tires which feature a rubber coating on the upper surrounding surface. Additionally, the front of the tires is equipped with a stationary 360-degree swivel wheel. The motors were fixed to the acrylic plate by means of two slender acrylic holders, which were secured in place by screws. The acrylic plate was affixed with 3 cm spacers to mount the electronics, and finally, the 3D printed encoders were attached to the motors.

Fig. 4. Basic assembly of the vehicle

IV. CONSTRUCTION ELECTRONICS

The project framework utilizes an ESP-32 camera version and an Arduino Uno. A controller based on the Windows operating system was also utilized.

The vehicle houses two geared 3-6V DC (direct current) motors with a total weight of 100 grams. They have a gear ratio of 48:1. Provided with 6 volts, they consume 130–150 mA and create a torque of 1.1 kg/cm, moving at 175 rotations per minute.

Two HC-89 interrupt sensors with LM393 ICs were installed. This module is based on a non-contact sensing, photo-

interrupt detection slot sensor with a 5 mm slot gap and an operating voltage range of 3.5-7 (V). The module can be used to detect the presence or motion of objects in general. Figure 5 demonstrates the 3D-printed and mounted HC89 encoders.

Fig. 5. The 3D printed and mounted HC89 encoders

L298N driver module was used to drive the motors. It has two standard H-bridges and PWM (pulse width modulation), making it ideal for controlling the direction and speed of two motors simultaneously.

The ESP-32 Camera Version has built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capabilities, as well as a CH340G onboard programmer, so a wire with a micro USB port can be attached to program it. It has 16 GPIO (general purpose input/output) pins and operates at 3.3-5 volts (V). The Arduino Uno used here is the Revision 3 model that runs on 5-12 volts and has 16 IO (Input Output) pins as well as 6 analog input pins.

The battery used to power the vehicle is a 7.4 V Lithium Polymer with 30 C discharge, 2000 mAh storage capacity, and a maximum discharge current of 15 A.

The total weight of the vehicle is about 700 grams, and its dimensions are 30 × 15 × 7 cm (length x width x height in cm). Figure 6 shows the assembled final vehicle.

Fig. 6. Fully Assembled Vehicle

V. THE CIRCUIT OF THE AGV

The power is connected to a power switch, which, when closed, will allow electricity to pass through the circuit. The L298N is supplied with a direct voltage of 7.4 volts from the battery, whereas the ESP32 and Arduino Uno are supplied with a 5 volt input from the L298N output, which decreases the 7.4 volt input to 5 volts. Three of the ESP-32's pins are linked to

Arduino read pins. The HC-89 interrupt sensors are linked to Arduino interrupt handling pins 2 and 3.

Fig 7. Circuit diagram of the Vehicle [4]

VI. AGV SOFTWARE STRUCTURE

Both the microcontroller (ESP32 and Arduino Uno) operate alongside the computer, simultaneously running their respective code. The purpose of using two microcontrollers is to assign a specific task to each, ensuring the task is executed with minimal error and delay. The following outlines the functionality of each system component:

1. ESP 32 Cam

It is programmed using the C language in the Arduino Interpreter version 1.8.19. Configured in Wi-Fi station mode, the ESP 32 is assigned a specific URL (Universal Resource Locator) such as 192.168.10.7 in our case, assigned to the ESP 32 by the internet router. The same URL is used to receive direction commands from the computer. The ESP 32 source code is available on GitHub [5].

2. Computer

In the project, a Lenovo Ideapad 320 laptop was used to carry out the tests and to control the AGV because of its mobility and long battery life. It has the following specifications:

- Processor: Intel Core i5 7200U CPU 2.5 (GHz)
- RAM: 8 (GB) DDR3
- Video card: Nvidia GeForce 920MX 2GB Video Memory
- Built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth.

With these specs, by writing the code in python, it is easy to receive the input from the keyboard running pygame library and then send the control data over Wi-Fi to the same URL assigned to the ESP32-Cam. This is done in Visual Studio Code version 1.74.3 and Python version 3.10.9. The Python source code is available on GitHub [6].

3. Arduino Uno

Arduino Uno is programmed in the C language using the same Arduino interpreter as for the ESP32. The communication between ESP32 and Arduino was established using a set of 3 pins to cover all the possible directions the vehicle had to move. A unique sequence of

pins was made high (voltage above 3.3V is meant as HIGH), which was digitally read by the Arduino Uno, and it instructed the L298N to move the motors accordingly. The sequence and their interpreted command are given in the following table:

Sequence	Interpreted command
111	Forward
011	Backward
001	Right
101	Left
010	Extreme right
110	Extreme left
100	Stop
000	Return Home

Table 3. Sequence sent to Arduino for command

The Arduino source code is available on GitHub. [7]

Fig. 8. Flowchart of vehicle logic [3]

VII. DETERMINING DISTANCE AND DIRECTION

The HC-89 LM393 uses an infrared LED and a phototransistor to detect movement. A slotted disk is attached to the motor shaft and as the motor rotates, the slots pass through the LED and its sensor interrupting the infrared light.

Fig. 9. Slit count demonstration

Whenever a slot passes, the beam is either allowed or blocked through which creates a pulse. This is converted into a clean digital signal by the LM393 IC(Integrated Circuit) which acts as a comparator and produces either High (1) or LOW (0). This produces a square wave signal which varies with time. The pulse width is used to determine the speed of the motor for example if slits are passing through the encoder very quickly the pulse width decreases. The distance and orientation for the vehicle in our system is determined by the amount of pulses or slits passed through the encoder for each motor.

Fig. 10. Voltage Time Graph output from HC89 [10].

VIII. RETURN-TO-HOME LOGIC

Our system relies entirely on motor mounted encoders for return-to-home. As the vehicle (ESP32-Cam) receives motion commands during the manual operation mode, it simultaneously records and stores encoder counts for each motor and movement labels (like forward or back). All this data is stored sequentially to map the path taken by the vehicle. The encoder readings are always running in the background and captured using interrupts by Arduino ensuring precise and real-time logging.

When a return back command is received, the Arduino halts all current operations, finalizes the log, and starts retracing the original path. It starts reading and executing the stored movements in reverse order (last one first) and using complimentary motor actions (like backward for forward). The encoder counts are matched to ensure the autonomous return-to-home is distance accurate.

Fig. 11. Vehicle controlled manually and back to initial location autonomously

(Note: Yellow and Blue arrows are just to show the movement path of the car and are not present in the environment. Yellow shows the path of the vehicle moving up to the destination. The blue arrows show the movement path back to the initial location).

Fig. 12. Flowchart of the return-to-home logic

Process Counters:

This function calculates the number of encoder slits covered since the last recorded command by subtracting previous counts from the current encoder counts. It then stores the command along with the corresponding slit counts and directional symbols for both the left and right motors into storage arrays for later use during the return-to-home.

Return Back:

Read stored commands in reverse order and apply inverse motion

Fig. 13. Path during Manual mode and Autonomous Return-to-Home

Order of Command in Manual Mode			
No.	Command	LMSC	RMSC
1	Forward	+100	+100
2	Right	+110	+55
3	Extreme Left	+15	-15
4	Backward	-75	-75

Order of Command in its Return-to-Home Mode			
No.	Command	LMSC	RMSC
1	Forward	+75	+75
2	Extreme Right	-15	+15
3	Right Reverse	-110	-55
4	Backward	-100	-100

Table 4. Commands Storage and execution. LMSC: Left Motor Slit Count, RMSC: Right Motor Slit Count

IX. REAL LIFE APPLICATIONS OF RETURN TO HOME

This return-to-home technique demonstrates a viable and cost-effective alternate to conventional localization systems. It is especially useful in indoor or areas where GPS signals are not accessible. It is useful across a variety of domains which demand repeatability and accurate positioning.

This method can be useful in industrial settings where autonomous guided vehicles (AGVs) are used for tasks like cargo and orders transport as well as shelf management. These vehicles also require autonomously going back through complex areas back to recharging stations, supply points and performing task loops.

Similarly, it can be used in consumer-grade autonomous robots such as vacuum cleaners or lawn movers, as well as educational robots such as those used for time and distance sensitive line or shortest path following robots for consistent and fast return to home. Similarly, entertainment robots like domino stacking robots can also use this.

Another advantageous field to implement in is agricultural sector. These AGVs operate in confined spaces in greenhouses. In such cases, encoder-based return to home ensures accurate retracing back home after a seedling spraying or general inspection.

This technique avoids costly infrastructure preparation, heavy computational demands required for vision based, magnetic beacons or other mapping techniques. This power efficient with high precision makes it suitable for resource efficient platforms in diverse robotic applications.

X. CONCLUSION

This return-to-home vehicle model successfully meets most of the requirements of indoor and small-to-medium range distance travelling without using complicated and expensive methods utilizing highly precise GPS sensors, cameras and even gyro sensors as displayed in its operational video [12]. This simple and low-cost method has proven effective in completing the specialized task of returning the vehicle to its original starting position with high precision and negligible delay.

However, this system is not without its own set of limitations which require further improvements to allow it be used very reliably in industrial applications. Notably, the major limitation that we encountered was the wheel slip on uneven or slippery surfaces. This is a problem as this rotation of the motor is registered by the microcontroller as movement while in reality there has been no displacement of the vehicle. One solution might be to use better quality, high traction tyres in indoor environments. Another solution might be to upgrade the system from a two-motor powered system to a fully four-wheel drive system. This can then be used to compute the average of the two encoders on each side to obtain an average providing error-correction if one of the readings is incorrect due to individual sensor slippage errors.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare they have no conflict of interest.

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